

DIRECT EXAMINATION OF INTERPHASES IN MODEL COMPOSITES USING PHASE-STEPPING PHOTOELASTICITY

F.M. Zhao¹, F.R. Jones¹ and E.A. Patterson²

¹ *Ceramics and Composites Laboratory, Department of Engineering Materials, University of Sheffield, Mappin Street, Sheffield S1 3DJ, UK*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Michigan, USA*

SUMMARY: A phase-stepping photoelastic technique has been used to evaluate quantitatively the effect of an interphase region on interfacial shear stress at a fibre-break and hence the efficiency of the interfacial bond. E-glass fibres were coated with an epoxy resin of lower Young's modulus and yield strength than that of the matrix resin as well a plasma copolymer. This enables the effect of sizing or modified matrix region to be quantified. The micro-mechanical response in the matrix at the interface/interphase has been described in detail using contour maps of isochromatic fringe order. From these, the profile of the interfacial shear stress at fibre-breaks has been calculated. In the presence of an interphase region the stress transfer profile was modified and the stress concentration associated with a transverse crack reduced.

KEYWORDS: Photoelasticity, non-destructive testing, fragmentation test, epoxy coating, plasma-coating, interface/interphase, transverse matrix crack, single fibre composites.

INTRODUCTION

The fibre matrix interface in composite materials plays an important role in determining their mechanical properties and reliability. The interfacial response between a fibre and polymer matrix can be evaluated by quantifying the rate of stress transfer along the interface. Several micro-mechanical experiments, such as fibre fragmentation or pull-out have been coupled fibre Raman or fluorescence spectroscopy for the determination of fibre stress profile and hence the efficiency of the stress transfer at a break. The data analysis relies on certain theoretical models and associated assumptions for the calculation of interfacial shear strength or a related parameter. The results are often contradictory because the assumptions employed in the chosen model are invalid [1]. Furthermore, the use of Raman and fluorescence spectroscopy is limited to certain types of fibres, such as high modulus carbon and polymer fibres and transparent non-fluorescent resins. Furthermore the fragmentation test can only be used with polymer matrices of high failure strain. Since normal practical resins have low failure strains fragmentation often employs a model matrix. On the other hand, fracture events, such as interfacial debonding and transverse matrix cracking, which occur at a fibre-end or a fibre-break, are very informative about the likely failure mechanism. For example, the debond can propagate along the bonded interface with increasing load but this event cannot be readily examined using the fragmentation test or Raman spectroscopy. Since the shear yield stress and Young's modulus of the matrix resin determines the rate of stress transfer to the fibre and the maximum shear stress that the interface or interphase can withstand without debonding or matrix yield in the interphase region, the interfacial shear

strength obtained from the fragmentation test can be rather difficult to interpret [2-3]. It is therefore timely to examine experimentally the stress field in the matrix near the debonded and the bonded interface.

The photoelastic technique has been used for measuring experimentally the stress field in a matrix from which the shear stress distribution at the interface for single-fibre epoxy model composites can be obtained [4-8]. Recently, a phase-stepping automated polariscope has been combined with a mini-loading frame and microscope to measure the stress field in the matrix around a fibre-end or near a fibre-break [7, 8]. The instrument can capture simultaneously the four images needed to produce maps of isochromatic and isoclinic parameters over a full field of view at several levels of applied load. The automatic polariscope allows real-time data to be obtained during fibre fracture and interfacial debonding, from which stress contour maps can be constructed. In this case, interfacial debonding and matrix cracking can be readily identified and quantified.

In the present study, single fibre model composite specimens consisting of a short E-glass fibre embedded in an epoxy resin have been studied. E-glass fibres were coated with a low Young's modulus epoxy resin or plasma-copolymer to create different interphases between the fibre and matrix. A cold-cured epoxy resin was chosen to avoid the induction of a residual thermal stress on cooling from the cure temperature. In this paper, phase-stepping photoelasticity is used to examine precisely the interfacial response at the fibre-breaks in a single fibre composite under an axial tensile and evaluate quantitatively the interfacial adhesion between the coated and non-coated glass fibres.

PHASE-STEPPING PHOTOELASTICITY

A typical arrangement of the optical device and light-path is shown in refs [7-8]. The new instrument, whose principle has been reported elsewhere [7,9], is equipped with four CCD cameras for collecting the photoelastic images simultaneously. A filter which only transmits light of wavelength of 542 ± 5 nm was used to produce an essentially monochromatic green source. Cubic beam-splitters have been used to provide four elliptically polarized light beams, which are interrogated by quarter-wave plates and analysers. The pairs of quarter-wave plates and analysers are orientated so as to generate four phase-steps in the photoelastic data. The four signals can be readily processed by a multiplexer to combine them into a single composite image that can be digitized by a single frame-grabber and recorded on hard disk of a computer. The composite image can be subsequently re-divided into four images so that a phase-stepping algorithm can be implemented. In phase-stepping photoelasticity, the isoclinic angle, \mathbf{q} and the relative retardation, \mathbf{d} are given by solving the light intensity equations of the four phase-stepped images [6-7],

$$\mathbf{q} = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{i_2 - i_3}{i_2 + i_3 - 2i_1} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{d} = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{i_2 - i_3}{\sin 2\mathbf{q} (i_2 + i_3 - 2i_4)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where i_1 to i_4 are the light intensities observed by each CCD camera. The relative retardation, d in the specimen is related to the fringe order [11], N , by

$$d = 2pN \quad (3)$$

The isochromatic fringe order, N , can be obtained as a fractional value by the combining eqs (2) and (3). The fractional value can be identified by the unwrapped algorithm and then converted into an absolute fringe order by the operator [7]. In photoelasticity, the relationship between the isochromatic fringe order, N , and the principal stresses \mathbf{s}_1 and \mathbf{s}_2 , or maximum shear stress, \mathbf{t}_{\max} , in a two dimensional model can be written as [11]

$$\mathbf{t}_{\max} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}_2) = \frac{Nf_s}{2t} \quad (4)$$

where t is the thickness of the sample and f_s is the stress-fringe constant of a material. \mathbf{t}_{\max} is the average collection of the light intensity through the full thickness of the sample and therefore needs correction [4, 6]. Hence, interfacial shear stress along the fibre direction can be obtained from Eqn 5 [4, 6]

$$\mathbf{t}_i = \mathbf{t}_{c\max} \sin 2q \quad (5)$$

The images are digitised into a matrix of 256×256 pixels and transferred to a computer that processes the data. For each pixel in the picture, equations (1) to (2) are used to obtain the isoclinic angle and then the relative retardation. These result in maps of the periodic parameters that can be converted into contours of continuous fringe order using the unwrapping algorithms [9]. Interfacial shear stresses can be calculated from Eqns (4) and (5).

EXPERIMENTAL

Uncoated unsized E-glass fibres used in this study were manufactured by the Institute of Polymer Research Dresden, Germany. The Young's modulus and diameter of the fibre are 72 GPa and 80 μm , respectively. Single fibre composite (SFC) specimens consisting of a short E-glass fibre embedded in Araldite LY 5052 epoxy resin cured with 38 phr of Aradur HY 5052 hardener (Ciba-Geigy). The resin cured at room temperature for at least 7 days. The resin had a Young's modulus of 3.2 GPa and tensile strength of 73 MPa. To investigate the interfacial response of an E-glass fibre in the presence of a soft interphase, it was coated with an epoxy resin of lower Young's modulus and yield strength. The epoxy used for coating was a mixture of Araldite LY1556 and Araldite GY 298, cured with nadic methylene anhydride (NMA) and Capcure 3-380, a mercaptan terminated polymer. The coating resin had a Young's modulus of 2.1 GPa and tensile strength of 41 MPa. To create different interphases, E-glass fibres were coated by using plasma polymerization with a cross-linked conformal film of 90% acrylic acid and 10% 1,7 octadiene. All single fibre composite specimens were subjected to uniaxial tension in the fibre direction to achieve fibre fragmentation. The loading was interrupted temporarily at intervals of applied matrix stress to capture photoelastic images in the matrix near the ends of the fragments. Four images then were processed to obtain isochromatic fringe order and isoclinic angle using Eqns. (1) ~ (3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Epoxy-coated fibres

Fig. 1 shows the contour maps of fringe order in the matrix near a fibre-break for the epoxy-coated glass fibre at two applied matrix stresses: 8.56 and 12.42 MPa. The continuous isochromatic pattern is shown using twelve colours from blue to white. The twelve colours also have the relevant numerical scale indicating the value of the fringe order. The dimensions of the matrix region are approximately 0.85 by 0.50 mm. For the epoxy-coated fibre, the matrix crack initiated by the fibre-break is very small (17 μm long) compared with non-coated fibre [12]. The epoxy used for the coating has lower Young's modulus, which can create a relatively tough interphase. It has been observed that this "synthetic" interphase controlled the propagation of a matrix crack from the fibre-break. But no interfacial debonding was observed. It can be seen that at 8.56 MPa, the highest stress concentration appears in the matrix around the crack tip at the end of the broken fibre. At 12.42 MPa, the stress concentration zone became smaller. This is in contrast to the extension of the stress concentration zone in the matrix near a crack at the higher stress for the non-coated glass, and Al_2O_3 fibre composites [7, 8]. This can be explained by examining the profiles of interfacial shear stress for non-coated and coated fibres.

Fig 1: Contour maps of fringe order in the matrix near a fibre-break and a matrix crack for epoxy-coated glass fibre at applied matrix stress: (a) 8.56 and (b) 12.42 MPa (Fragment length 11.03 mm)

Fig 2 shows the profiles of interfacial shear stress calculated from the fringe order data in Fig. 1 and the measured isoclinic angles at the interface. It can be seen that the shear stress was not zero at the end of the fibre-break as observed in previous studies [6, 7, 8]. We observed that the interfacial shear stress from the end of a break rose up to a maximum value always over a distance for different single fibre composites. The transverse matrix crack firstly determines the locality of the maximum interfacial shear stress [8,13] and then interfacial debonding [8]. At applied stresses of 8.56 and 12.42 MPa, the maximum in interfacial shear stress occurred at 0.09 mm and 0.124 mm from the break, respectively. In this case, a much shorter matrix crack (17 μm) formed on fibre fracture thereby perturbing the shear transfer zone to a lesser extent. For the epoxy-coated glass fibre, it can be seen that shear stress at the end of the broken fibre is much lower than that observed for the non-coated fibre at a similar applied stresses [12], indicating a tough interphase. There is a low shear stress near the fibre-end insufficient to cause debonding, which was not observed. This phenomenon can be attributed to localised yield in the interphasal region. The maximum shear stress can only be generated at the interface, where yield did not occur. This is similar to previous observations [6, 8]. Fig 2 also gives the profile of interfacial shear stress for the epoxy-coated fibre when the applied matrix stress had reached 17.64 MPa. The targeted fragment had become much shorter at 0.92 mm because of an additional fibre-break. The maximum interfacial shear stress drops dramatically because the fragment is too short to be fully loaded. A relatively high interfacial shear stress was generated at the other end of the fragment, which has modified the interfacial shear stress profiles.

Fig.2: Profiles of interfacial shear stress determined by photoelastic analysis for epoxy-coated glass fibre at 8.56 MPa ($L_f = 11.03$ mm), 12.42 MPa ($L_f = 11.03$ mm) and 17.64 MPa ($L_f = 0.92$ mm)

Plasma-coated fibres

Fig. 3 shows the contour map of fringe order in the matrix near a fibre-break for the plasma-coated fibre at an applied matrix stress of 12.24 MPa. A larger transverse matrix crack formed and its length is approximately 66 μm . Interfacial debonding at the ends of the broken fibres was observed at higher external loads. It can be seen that at the similar matrix stress, the stress

concentration zone around the plasma-coated fibre is much larger than that of the epoxy-coated fibre.

Fig 3: Contour maps of fringe order in the matrix near a fibre-break and a matrix crack for plasma-coated glass fibre at applied matrix stress of 12.18 MPa ($L_f = 3.45$ mm)

Fig.4: Profiles of interfacial shear stress determined by photoelastic analysis for plasma-coated glass fibre at applied matrix stress of 12.24 MPa, $L_f = 2.35$ mm

Fig. 4 shows the distribution of interfacial shear stress calculated using the fringe order in Fig 3. For the plasma-coated glass fibre, the maximum value of interfacial shear stress is 17.69 MPa, which is higher than that of epoxy-coated fibre at the similar load. The interfacial shear stress rose up to the maximum over a longer distance of 0.16 mm from the break.

The previous results demonstrate that in the presence of the modified interphase region the stress transfer process was modified and the stress concentration associated with a transverse

crack reduced depending on a tough interphase. The maximum in interfacial shear stress occurs at the point along the interface when the fibre is reloaded through stress transfer.

CONCLUSIONS

Phase-stepping photoelastic analysis has been used to measure the micro-stress field in the matrix and at the interface around the ends of fibre-breaks for the epoxy-coated and plasma-coated E-glass fibres, at different applied matrix stresses. The automatic polariscope allows real-time data to be obtained during fibre fracture, from which stress contour maps can be constructed on the micro scale and interfacial shear stress can be calculated. This technique enables full profiles of the stress field in the matrix at the interface to be obtained quantitatively for complex situations where a transverse matrix crack has formed and where an interphase region has yielded locally. Automated photoelasticity with phase-stepping technology has proved to be a useful tool for the direct determination of interphase information in single fibre epoxy composites.

It is clearly shown that in the absence of interfacial failure through debonding interphasal yield can modify the stress transfer back to the fibre at a fibre-break. A thin layer of sizing resin can reduce the impact of a transverse matrix crack, which forms at a fibre break, on the stress transfer mechanism. In this case the fragment could be reloaded to fracture, illustrating the change in the stress transfer efficiency. This has a major impact on the description of the stress state near a fibre-break and hence on the predictive methods for composite strength. The design of the interphase region associated with sizings or interfacially induced phase separation can be used to optimise the strength and reliability of a composite material.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is supported by the EPSRC portfolio grant. We thank the Advanced Composites Group for supplying epoxy resins and Prof K. Schulte of Technical University Hamburg-Harburg for supplying E-glass fibres. We thank Dr A.C. Johnson and Mr H. Sugihara for coating E-glass fibres.

REFERENCES

1. Tripathi, D. and Jones, F.R., "Measurement of the load-bearing capability of the fibre-matrix interface by single-fibre fragmentation", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 57, No. 8, 1997, PP. 925-935.
2. Tripathi, D. and Jones, F.R., "Review, Single fibre fragmentation test for assessing adhesion in fibre reinforced composites", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 33, No. 1, 1998, pp. 1-16.
3. Zhao, F.M., Okabe, T. and Takeda, N., "Effect of matrix yield properties on fragmentation behaviour of single fibre composites", *Composite Interface*, Vol. 9, No. 3, 2002, pp. 289-308.
4. Schuster, D.M. and Scala, E., "The mechanical interaction of sapphire whiskers with a birefringent matrix", *Transactions of the metallurgical society of AIME*, Vol. 230, 1964, pp. 1635-1640.

5. Tyson, W.R. and Davies, G.J., "A photoelastic study of the shear stresses associated with the transfer of stress during fibre reinforcement", *British Journal of Applied Physics.*, Vol.16, 1965, pp. 199-205.
6. Fiedler, B. and Schulte, K., "Photoelastic analysis of fibre-reinforced model composite materials", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 57, No. 8, 1997, pp. 859-867.
7. Zhao, F.M., Hayes, S.A., Patterson, A.E., Young R.J. and Jones F.R., "Measurement of micro stress fields in epoxy matrix around a fibre using phase-stepping automated photoelasticity", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 63, No. 12, 2003, pp. 1783-1787.
8. Zhao, F.M., Martin, R.D.S., Hayes, S.A., Patterson, E.A., Young, R.J. and Jones, F.R., "Photoelastic analysis of matrix stresses around a high modulus sapphire fibre by means of phase-stepping automated polariscope", *Composites Part A*, Vol. 36, No. 2, 2004, pp. 229-244.
9. Patterson, E.A. and Wang, Z.F., "Simultaneous observation of phase-stepped images for automated photoelasticity", *Journal of Strain Analysis*, Vol. 33, No. 1, 1998, pp. 1-15.
10. Dally, J.W. and Riley, W.F., *Experimental stress analysis*, New York: McGraw-Hill, 1985.
11. Zhao, F.M., Hayes, S.A., Patterson, E.A., Young, R.J. and Jones, F.R. "Photoelastic analysis of resin matrix stress near fibre-end and broken fibre in fragmentation test", *SME Technical paper* (EM03-364), Composites Manufacturing Association of the Society of Manufacturing Engineers, 2003.
12. Zhao, F.M., Jones, F.R. and Patterson, E.A., "Phase-stepping photoelasticity for quantifying the interfacial response in fibre composites at fibre-breaks", *Materials Science and Engineering*, in press.
13. Liu, H.Y., Mai, Y.W., Ye, L. and Zhou, L.M., "Stress transfer in the fibre fragmentation test. Part III: effect of matrix cracking and interface debonding", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 32, No. 3, 1997, pp.633-41.